

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FLOATING
TABLETS OF METOPROLOL TARTARATE BY USING
NATURAL POLYMERS****S.Rohini*¹, M. Ramya Teja ² and J. N. Suresh Kumar³**¹Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.³Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601**Abstract:**

The aim of present research work is to formulate and evaluate controlled release floating tablet of Metoprolol tartarate in view to enhance bioavailability and therapeutic action. The tablets were formulated by employing wet granulation method using PVP K 30 as binder and isopropyl alcohol as granulating fluid. The granules were evaluated for flow properties. All the formulations showed values within the prescribed limits for tests like hardness, friability and weight variation which indicate that the prepared tablets are of standard quality. All the tablets were formulated using sodium bicarbonate as effervescent agent. All the prepared formulations floated immediately after placing into the beaker and the floating was maintained more than 14 hrs. It was observed that the carbon dioxide generated from sodium bicarbonate in presence of dissolution medium (0.1N HCL) was trapped in the polymer gel matrix formed by the hydration of polymer which decreases the density (<1) and makes the tablet buoyant. The correlation coefficient values (r) revealed that the dissolution profiles followed Zero order kinetics and the mechanism of drug release was governed by Peppas model. The n values are found to be more than 0.5 (n>0.5) indicated that the drug release was predominantly controlled by non fickian diffusion. Based on the release rate constant and % of drug release the formulations prepared with Moringa oleifera shown prolonged retarding nature compared with the formulations prepared with Gum karayaleaves mucilage. Among all the formulations, F₃ formulation containing drug and Moringa oleifera in 1:1.5 ratio was found to be optimized formulations.

Key words: Metoprolol tartarate, Moringa oleifera, Gum karaya, Sodium bicarbonate

Corresponding author:

S.Rohini,
Research Scholar,
Department of Pharmaceutics,
Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601

QR code

Please cite this article in press S.Rohini et al., *Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating Tablets Of Metoprolol Tartarate By Using Natural Polymers.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (07).

INTRODUCTION:

Antihypertensive drugs have always been in the forefront of research because the cardiovascular disorders are on an increase globally. Now a day's millions of people are suffering from cardiac diseases and these drugs require chronic administration to get symptomatic relief¹.

Treatment for hypertension is a long term therapy where noncompliance is high; hence prolonged release dosage forms are required for quality health care. The hypertension condition requires the continuous availability of antihypertensive drug in the systemic circulation. Metoprolol tartarate is an Antihypertensive drug .It suppresses the effects of angiotensin II at its receptors, thereby blocking the rennin- angiotensin system. The rennin-angiotensin system plays a crucial role in the control of blood pressure, and in particular it is felt to play crucial role in hypertension. The molecular weight of Metoprolol tartarate is 461.01. It is freely soluble in water . It has low bioavailability due to its first pass metabolism. Systemic bioavailability is about 33%. The half life of Metoprolol tartarate is approximately 3 hrs. It has absorption window in the gastric region ².The objective of this study was to develop floating tablets of Metoprolol tartarate using natural polymer having desirable properties in order to achieve an extended retention in the upper gastrointestinal tract, which may result in enhanced absorption and there by improved bioavailability.

The gastroretentive drug delivery system can be retained in the stomach and assist in improving the oral sustained delivery of drugs. There is a need to investigate a number of indigenously available retardant material to make the concept of controlled release drug delivery more viable for the drug industry at more economical way³. In the present study, natural polymers such as Moringa oleifera and Gum karaya leaves mucilage were selected for the preparation of floating tablets of Metoprolol tartarate. Sodium bicarbonate was used as gas generating agent. Tablets were prepared by wet granulation method using these polymers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Metoprolol tartarate was obtained as a gratis sample from Hetero labs, Hyderabad. Gum karaya leaves mucilage and Moringa oleifera gum were purchased from Yucca enterprises, Mumbai. PVP K 30, Isopropyl alcohol and Sodium bicarbonate were purchased from Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai. All other ingredients were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets

Metoprolol tartarate was mixed with required quantities of Moringa oleifera/ Gum karaya , Sodium bicarbonate and Citric acid by geometric mixing . The tablets were formulated by employing wet granulation method using PVP K 30 as binder and isopropyl alcohol as granulating fluid. Magnesium stearate and talc were used as lubricant and glidant respectively. The final blend was compressed into tablets using 7 mm punches and corresponding dies on rotary tablet compression machine ⁶. The composition of each formulation was given in Tables 1.

Evaluation Parameters

Flow properties of granules: The granules were evaluated for the following parameters ⁷.

a) Bulk density: 5 gm of blend was weighed and transferred to a measuring cylinder. Then bulk volume was noted. Bulk density was calculated by using the following formula

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder}}{\text{Bulk volume}}$$

b) Tapped density: 5 gm of blend was weighed, transferred to a measuring cylinder and subjected to 100 tapings. Then volume was noted as tapped volume. Tapped density was measured by using the following formula

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder}}{\text{Tapped volume}}$$

c) Carr's index

Carr's index was calculated by using the following formula

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

d) Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio was calculated by using the following formula

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

e) Angle of repose

5 gm of blend was taken and poured into a hollow cylinder which was placed on a graph sheet. Then the cylinder was slowly lifted. Then height and diameter of the heap formed were noted down. The angle of repose (θ) was calculated by the formula

$$\text{Angle of repose, } \theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{h}{r}$$

Evaluation of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets

a) Hardness: The hardness of the tablet was measured by Monsanto hardness tester. The lower plunger was placed in contact with the tablet and a zero reading was taken. The plunger was then forced against a spring by tuning a threaded bolt until the tablet fractured. As the spring was compressed a pointer rides along a gauge in the barrel to indicate the force⁸. The hardness was measured in terms of kg/cm².

b) Weight variation: Formulated tablets were tested for weight uniformity, 20 tablets were weighed collectively and individually. From the collective weight, average weight was calculated⁸. The percent weight variation was calculated by using the following formula.

$$\% \text{Variation} = \frac{\text{Average Wt} - \text{Individual Wt}}{\text{Average Wt}} \times 100$$

c) Friability: The Roche friability test apparatus was used to determine the friability of the tablets. Twenty two pre-weighed tablets were placed in the apparatus and operated for 100 revolutions and then the tablets were reweighed. The percentage friability was calculated according to the following formula⁸.

$$\text{Friability} = \frac{\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

d) Swelling Index: Formulated tablets were weighed individually (W₀) and placed separately in Petri dish containing 50 ml of 0.1N Hydrochloric acid. The Petri dishes were placed in an incubator maintained at 37±0.5°C. The tablets were removed from the petri dish, at predefined intervals of time and reweighed (W_t), and the % swelling index was calculated using the following formula⁹:

$$\% W_U = \frac{(W_t - W_0)}{W_0} \times 100$$

Where:

W_U – Water uptake

W_t – Weight of tablet at time t

W₀ – Weight of tablet before immersion

e) In vitro buoyancy study : This test is characterized by floating lag time and total floating time. The test was performed using USP-Type II paddle apparatus using 900 ml of 0.1N Hydrochloric acid at paddle rotation of 100 rpm at 37 ± 0.5°C. The time required for tablet to rise to surface of dissolution medium and duration of time the tablet constantly float on dissolution medium was noted as floating lag time and total floating time¹⁰.

f) Drug content: 20 tablets were weighed and powdered the powder weight equivalent to 40mg of Metoprolol tartarate was dissolved in 100ml of 0.1N Hydrochloric acid and filtered. 5ml of this was diluted to 50ml with water and drug content was estimated at 254nm by UV spectrophotometer¹¹.

g) In vitro dissolution test: The release of Metoprolol tartarate from the tablet was studied using USP-Type II paddle apparatus. Drug release profile was carried out in 900 ml of 0.1N Hydrochloric acid maintained at 37 ± 0.5°C temperatures at 100 rpm. 5 ml of samples were withdrawn at regular time intervals. The samples was replaced by its equivalent volume of dissolution medium and was filtered through 0.45 µm Whatman filter paper and analyzed at 254 nm by UV spectrophotometer¹².

Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies: Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy studies were used for the evaluation of physicochemical compatibility and interactions, which helps in the prediction of interaction of the drug with Moringa oleifera/ Gum karaya leaves mucilage used in tablet formulations¹³.

Stability studies of optimized floating matrix tablets: The optimized floating matrix tablets were separated in to two groups. Each group of formulations were placed separately in stability chamber which is maintained at 25±5°C/60% RH and 40±5°C/75% RH respectively for three months and every month the formulations from each group were subjected to dissolution studies and % drug release was calculated¹⁴.

Results and Discussion:

Floating tablets of Metoprolol tartarate were prepared by varying the concentration of Moringa oleifera (F₁-F₃) and Gum karaya (F₄-F₆). The formulated granules were evaluated for various flow properties. The bulk density for all the formulations ranged from 0.525 to 0.532. The angle of repose for all the formulations was found to be in the range of 26°45'-27°91'. The Carr's index for all the formulations ranged from 15.33 – 15.94%. The value of bulk density indicates good packing characters. The value of angle of repose (25°-30°) for all the formulations indicates good flow property. The value of Carr's index (10-16%) indicates free flowing material. The values of Hausner's ratio were found to be between 1.182-1.189. The powder blend with Hauser's ratio of 1.25 has good flow properties. So the values indicate that the granules had acceptable flow properties. The flow properties were shown in table 2.

Floating matrix tablets were evaluated for hardness and friability. The hardness was found to be in between 4.3 – 4.7 kg. The tablets satisfied friability requirement, as the % friability values were less than 1%. The drug content estimations showed values in the range of 99.87 to 100.11%, which reflects good uniformity in drug content among different formulations. All the tablets passed weight variation test as the % weight variation was within the Pharmacopoeia limits of $\pm 5\%$ of the weight. All the formulations showed values within the prescribed limits for tests like hardness, friability and weight variation which indicate that the prepared tablets are of standard quality.

All the tablets were formulated using sodium bicarbonate as effervescent agent. All the prepared formulations floated immediately after placing into the beaker and the floating was maintained more than 14 hrs. It was observed that the carbon dioxide generated from sodium bicarbonate in presence of dissolution medium (0.1N HCL) was trapped in the polymer gel matrix formed by the hydration of polymer which decreases the density (< 1) and makes the tablet buoyant. The results of various physical properties and *in vitro* buoyancy studies were tabulated in table 3.

In vitro dissolution studies of all the formulations of floating matrix tablets were carried out in 0.1N HCL. The study was performed for 12 hrs and the cumulative drug release was calculated. All the formulations remained floating and intact throughout the dissolution studies. The formulations (F₁-F₃) containing Moringa oleifera showed decrease in drug release with increase in concentration of Moringa oleifera. The drug release from formulation F₃ containing drug and natural polymer in 1:1.5 ratio showed a maximum drug release at end of 11 hours. The dissolution profile for the formulations F₁- F₃ was shown in figure 1. The formulations (F₄-F₆) containing Gum karaya leaves mucilage showed decrease in drug release with increase in concentration of Gum karaya leaves mucilage. The drug release from formulation F₆ containing drug and natural polymer in 1:1.5 ratio showed a maximum drug release at end of 10 hours. The dissolution profile for the formulations F₄- F₆ was shown in figure 2.

To ascertain the mechanism of drug release, the dissolution data was analyzed by zero order, first order, and Higuchi and Peppas equations. The correlation coefficient values (r) revealed that the dissolution profiles followed Zero order kinetics and the mechanism of drug release was governed by

Peppas model. The n values are found to be more than 0.5 ($n > 0.5$) indicated that the drug release was predominantly controlled by non fickian diffusion. The *in-vitro* drug release kinetic data was shown in Table 4. The swelling index studies showed a gradual increase with increase in concentration of natural polymer and were shown in Table 5.

The characteristics peaks confirmed the structure of Metoprolol tartarate. The same peaks were also reported in all drug loaded matrix tablet. There were no change or shifting of the characteristic peaks in matrix tablets suggested that there was no significant drug polymer interaction which indicates the stable nature of the drug in all formulations. Drug release from optimized formulations before and after storage under varying conditions were evaluated periodically at the regular interval of every month. The drug release profiles of all the formulations did not change significantly after storage at $25 \pm 2^\circ \text{C} / 60 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ and $40 \pm 2^\circ \text{C} / 75 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ for a period of 3 months. There is no significant difference in the drug content and release rate constants. The results indicated that the drug release from the optimized formulations were found to be quite stable.

From the above results, it is clearly evident that the *in vitro* release of Metoprolol tartarate from the floating tablet was influenced by nature of natural polymer. Based on the release rate constant and % of drug release the formulations prepared with Moringa oleifera shown prolonged retarding nature compared with the formulations prepared with Gum karaya. Among all the formulations, F₃ formulation containing drug and Moringa oleifera in 1:1.5 ratio was found to be optimized formulations.

REFERENCES:

1. Ashok kumar D, Guru prasad M. Formulation and *in vitro* evaluation of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets by lipid solid dispersion spray drying technique. International journal of research in pharmacy and chemistry 2012;2(4):996-1000.
2. Patel DM, Patel MJ, Patel AN, Patel CN. Formulation and evaluation of mixed matrix gastro-retentive drug delivery for Metoprolol tartarate. Int J Pharma Investig 2011;1:247-254.
3. Gnanaprakash K., Chandhra Shekhar K B, Madhu Sudhana Chetty C. Floating tablets of Metoprolol tartarate with natural polymer: An approach for gastric treatment. J. Pharm. Sci. & Res. 2010;2 (10):657-662.
4. Ravi Kumar, Patil M B, Patil S R, Mahesh S. P. Formulation and Evaluation of Effervescent Floating Tablet of Metoprolol tartarate.

- International Journal of PharmTech Research 2009; 1(3):754-763.
5. Patel Manish P , Patel Madhabhai. M , Patel Dipti H , Patel Krishnakumar N. Formulation Development, Optimization and Evaluation of Metoprolol tartarate Floating Matrix Tablets International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research 2009; 1(2): 85-90.
 6. Jaimini M, Rana AC, Tanwar YS. Formulation and evaluation of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets. *Curr Drug Deliv* 2007;4(1):51-5.
 - 7..Shivanand Pandey, Viral Devmurari. Development and *In Vitro* Evaluation of Propranolol Hydrochloride Based Gastro-Retentive Floating Tablet. *Der Pharmacia Lettre* 2010; 2 (1): 75-86.
 8. Narendra C, Jain S, Srinath MS, Reddy SN, Sindhu A. Development of a Floating Dosage Form of Ranitidine Hydrochloride by Statistical Optimization Technique. *J Young Pharm.* 2010 ; 2(4): 342-349.
 9. Swapna Velivela, Sashmitha Samuel.B, Konde Abbulu. Formulation and evaluation of floating ranitidine hydrochloride tablets by using moringa gum as a functionality carrier. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 2012; 16(2): 116-120.
 10. Natasha Sharma, Neelam Balekar, Jain D K. Design and Development of Floating Tablet of Ranitidine Hydrochloride and Study the Effect of Formulation Variables. *Indian Journal of Novel Drug delivery*, 2011;3(4): 296-302.
 11. Gharti KP, Thapa P, Budhathki U, Bhargava A. Formulation and invitro evaluation of floating tablets of hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose and polyethylene oxide using ranitidine hydrochloride as a model drug. *J Young pharmacists*, 2012;4:201-8.
 12. Ashokkumar D, Guru Prasad M. Formulation and *In vitro* Evaluation of Ranitidine HCl Floating Tablets by Lipid Solid Dispersion Spray Drying Technique. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences*, 2012;3(4):1745-1751.
 - 13.. Prajapatia S, Patel L and Patel C. Floating matrix tablets of domperidone formulation and optimization using simplex lattice design. *Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2011, 10 (3), 447-455.
 14. Sarojini Sarangapani, Manavalan Rajappan. Lansoprazole Release from a Floating Dosage Form based on the Natural Polymer of Delonix regia. *International Journal of PharmTech Research* 2012;4(3):1084-1095.

Table 1: Composition of Metoprolol tartaratefloating tablets formulated with different natural polymers.

Ingredients	F ₁ (mg)	F ₂ (mg)	F ₃ (mg)	F ₄ (mg)	F ₅ (mg)	F ₆ (mg)
Losartan	50	50	50	50	50	50
Moringa oleifera	25	50	75			
Gum karaya				25	50	75
Micro crystalline cellulose	85	60	40	85	60	40
Sodium bicarbonate	50	50	50	50	50	50
Citricacid	25	25	25	25	25	25
Poly Vinyl pyrolidine	10	10	10	10	10	10
Magnesium stearate	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Talc	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Total weight	250	250	250	250	250	250

Table 2: Micromeritic properties of granules of Metoprolol tartaratefloating tablets formulated with different concentrations of natural polymers.

Formulation code	Angle of repose (°)	Bulk density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped density (gm/cm ³)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F ₁	27.14	0.525	0.623	15.73	1.16
F ₂	28.38	0.528	0.625	15.52	1.13
F ₃	29.26	0.530	0.626	15.33	1.15
F ₄	27.14	0.527	0.627	15.94	1.16
F ₅	29.14	0.530	0.629	15.73	1.16
F ₆	25.14	0.532	0.630	15.55	1.14

Table 3: Physical properties of Metoprolol tartaratefloating tablets formulated with different concentrations of natural polymers.

Formulation	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Weight variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)	Floating Lag time	Total floating time (hrs)
F ₁	4.77	250±2.13	0.37	100.15	156	>14
F ₂	4.8	250±1.47	0.62	99.45	134	>14
F ₃	4.7	251±2.39	0.37	101.89	128	>14
F ₄	4.77	250±1.45	0.37	100.15	164	>14
F ₅	4.80	251± 2.39	0.73	100.78	136	>14
F ₆	4.43	250± 1.98	0.52	99.62	124	>14

Table 4: *In vitro* drug release kinetic data of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets formulated with different concentrations of natural polymers

Formulation	Correlation Coefficient Value				Release Rate Constant (mg/hr) k_0	Exponential Coefficient (n)	T ₅₀ (hr)	T ₉₀ (hr)
	Zero Order	First Order	Matrix	Peppas				
F ₁	0.9916	0.8094	0.9581	0.9984	6.25	0.8756	4	7.2
F ₂	0.9943	0.7903	0.9632	0.9979	5.5	0.7938	4.54	8.1
F ₃	0.9957	0.7956	0.9780	0.9912	4.99	0.7455	5.01	9.01
F ₄	0.9894	0.8304	0.9581	0.9984	6.66	0.8147	3.75	6.75
F ₅	0.9910	0.8573	0.9612	0.9976	5.88	0.8206	4.25	7.65
F ₆	0.9939	0.8190	0.9751	0.9966	5.26	0.9188	4.75	8.55

Figure 1: Comparative *in vitro* drug release profile of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets formulated with different concentrations of Moringa oleifera

(-♦-) Floating tablets formulated with drug and Moringa oleifera in 1:0.5 ratio

(-■-) Floating tablets formulated with drug and Moringa oleifera in 1:1 ratio

(-▲-) Floating tablets formulated with drug and Moringa oleifera in 1:1.5 ratio

Figure 2: Comparative *in vitro* drug release profile of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablets formulated with different concentrations of Gum karaya

- (◆)-Floating tablets formulated with drug and Gum karaya in1:0.5 ratio
 (■)-Floating tablets formulated with drug and Gum karaya in1:1 ratio
 (▲)- Floating tablets formulated with drug and Gum karaya in1:1.5 ratio

Figure 3 - FTIR spectrum of Metoprolol tartarate

Figure 4- FTIR spectrum of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablet prepared with *Moringa oleifera*

Figure 5 - FTIR spectrum of Metoprolol tartarate floating tablet prepared with Gum karaya

